

Ionospheric Effects During Moderate Earthquake in Japan on September 5, 2018

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ABSTRACT

The Earth's interior layers, atmosphere, ionosphere, and magnetosphere (EAIM) constitute an interconnected system that is open, dynamic, and nonlinear. In this paper, the response of the ionosphere to a moderate earthquake of Richter magnitude $M \approx 6.6$ that occurred on 5 September 2018 in Japan was revealed. A multi-frequency, multiple-path coherent radio system at Harbin Engineering University (HEU complex) was used to observe the time-varying characteristics of HF radio waves along 14 radio propagation paths over the People's Republic of China. The Doppler spectra, the Doppler shift of the main mode frequency, and signal amplitudes are analyzed in the frequency range of 6-7 MHz in this paper. Our findings show that the seismic shock was followed by the spreading of Doppler spectra, and the Doppler frequency shift of the main mode varying with time in a quasi-periodic manner with an approximate period of 3 minutes for infrasound and 20-30 minutes for atmospheric gravity waves. The delay time of the assumed response and the apparent speed of propagation of the disturbances were estimated. Two additional moderate earthquakes with epicenters under water were used for comparison to analyze the influence of geographical factors. Ionograms are used to analyze the effect of ionospheric structure on disturbance propagation. Our study highlights the need to explore the direct and reverse, positive and negative linkages among the subsystems within the EAIM system to better understand the dynamics of this interconnected system.

Keywords: Earthquake, Ionosphere, Multi-Frequency Multiple-Path Coherent Radio System, Doppler Spectrum, Doppler Shift of Frequency, Quasi-Periodic Disturbance

1. INTRODUCTION

Seismic activity is a significant source of energy release that affects the subsystems of the tectonosphere-atmosphere-ionosphere-magnetosphere system (Chernogor, 2011). In the mid-1960s, it was discovered that seismic, infrasonic, and atmospheric gravity waves activate the interaction of these subsystems. Various ground-based and ground-space methods have been used to experimentally study seismo-ionospheric effects, and wave disturbances in the ionosphere generated by seismic activity have been confirmed (Guo *etc.*, 2019; Luo *etc.*, 2020a, b). However, it is still unclear how seismo-ionospheric effects depend on atmospheric and space weather conditions and earthquake magnitude and depth. Moreover, the ionospheric response to an earthquake is influenced by a multitude of factors, including the state of space and atmospheric weather, the time of year and day, and the geographic location of the epicenter. For instance, the ionospheric response can be significantly affected by the presence of a geomagnetic storm (Chernogor *etc.*, 2020) or solar eclipse (Guo *etc.*, 2020), as well as the season and local time. Furthermore, the location of the epicenter with respect to the geomagnetic equator, the ionospheric height, and the strength of the geomagnetic field also play a critical role.

This paper studies how a moderate earthquake of Richter magnitude $M \approx 6.6$ can affect radio waves in the Earth's ionosphere. A multi-frequency multiple-path coherent radio system was used to analyze temporal variations in Doppler spectra, Doppler shift of frequency, and signal amplitudes. It was found that the earthquake caused disturbances in the ionosphere that were detectable up to 1000 km away, and that these disturbances had quasi-periodic patterns with periods of ~ 3 minutes and ~ 20 -30 minutes. Furthermore, the observation results of the earthquake on 5 September 2018 (the epicenter was on land) and the observation results of the earthquakes on 7 July 2018 and 11 April 2019 (the epicenter was under the sea) were compared

and analyzed. The results show that the difference in source location has a significant impact on the Doppler spectrum of radio path.

2. BASIS AND EQUIPMENT

Our focus of research is the earthquake that occurred in Japan (42.686°N, 141.929°E) at UT 18:07:59 on 5 September 2018, which had a magnitude of approximately 6.6 on the Richter scale and an epicenter depth of $h \approx 35$ km. It is noteworthy that the seismic impact occurred 1-2 hours before sunrise at ionospheric heights, coinciding with the movement of the solar terminator, which may have affected the reaction to the earthquake. We also selected two other moderate earthquakes that occurred in Japan on 7 July 2018 (35.107°N, 140.42°E, UT 11:23:50, $M \approx 5.9$, $h \approx 40$ km) and on 11 April 2019 (40.41°N, 143.298°E, UT 08:18:21, $M \approx 6.0$, $h \approx 18$ km) for comparison. Figure 1 and Table 1 present the specific information and characteristic parameters of these three earthquakes. We used data from oblique sounding of the HEU complex and vertical sounding at the Yamagawa ionosonde station in Japan https://wdc.nict.go.jp/IONO/HP2009/contents/Ionosonde_Map_E.html to study the moderate earthquake. The distribution of the measuring stations is shown in Figure 1.

Two radio paths (Hwaseong-Harbin at 6015 kHz and Goyang-Harbin at 6600 kHz) with similar azimuths ($\sim 179^\circ$) over China (shown in Figure 1) were selected to analyze the temporal variations in the characteristics of high-frequency (HF) radio waves which accompanied the moderate earthquakes in Japan on 7 July 2018, 5 September 2018 and 11 April 2019. Since the midpoints of the two radio paths are at similar distances from the three epicenters ($D \approx 1400$ km; 1279 km; 1415 km), it is reasonable to expect that the responses in the ionosphere caused by the earthquakes will have a similar effect on the two paths, i.e., the time-variations of the Doppler spectra of the two paths should be approximately similar during the three earthquakes. The observation results are shown in Figure 4, which consistent with our expectation.

To investigate the reaction of the ionosphere to moderate (M 6) earthquakes with epicenters located approximately 1280-1415 km from the center of the radio path, further processing on the observations were performed. Guo etc. (2019) elaborated on the calculation of the apparent velocity of propagation of perturbations (v) based on time difference (Δt), and the derivation of relative perturbations of electron concentration (δN_d) based on quasi-periodic process frequency (f_{Dd}) calculation in previous work. The results of estimates for these earthquakes are given in Table. 1.

Figure 1. The distribution of measurement stations and epicenters.

Table 1. Main basic parameters and parameters of disturbances associated with earthquakes in Japan.

Date UT hh:mm:ss, dd.mm.yy; JST hh:mm:ss, dd.mm.yy.	Symbol	location of the epicenter	M	h , km	D , km	f_{Da} , Hz	T , min	δ_{Na} , %	ΔT , min
11:23:50, 07.07.18; 20:23:50, 07.07.18	●	35.107°N,140.42°E (under the ocean)	~5.9	~40	~1400	0.10–0.20 0.25–0.30	4–5 15–30	4–9 30–55	55 100
18:07:59, 05.09.18; 03:07:59, 06.09.18	●	42.686°N,141.929°E (on land)	~6.6	~35	~1279	0.05–0.10 0.20–0.25	3 30	1.5–3 6–7.5	30 150
08:18:21, 11.04.19; 17:18:21, 11.04.19	●	40.41°N,143.298°E (under the ocean)	~6.0	~18	~1415	0.10–0.12	15	25–30	60

3. SPACE WEATHER ANALYSIS

On the nights of September 3-4 and 6-7, 2018, the concentration of solar wind particles (n_{sw}) increased from 5×10^6 to 25×10^6 m⁻³, as shown in Figure 2. In addition, the velocity (V_{sw}) of the particles increased from ~400 to ~490 km/s, while the temperature (T_{sw}) rose from $\sim 0.5 \times 10^5$ to $\sim 2.6 \times 10^5$ K on September 5th and 7th, 2018. These changes resulted in an increase in dynamic pressure (p_{sw}) from 1.5-2.5 to 6.6 nPa. The azimuthal B_y and vertical B_z components of the interplanetary magnetic field experienced fluctuations ranging from -6.9 to 5.9 nT and from -4.4 to 9.4 nT, respectively.

Bursts in the Akasofu function, which represents the power entering the magnetosphere from the solar wind (ϵ_A), were observed on September 4th, 5th, and 7th, 2018, reaching values of 4.5-5.7 GJ/s. As a result, relatively small magnetic disturbances were observed on these dates, with the K_p index ranging from 2 to 3.3 and the D_{st} index fluctuating between -23 and 21 nT.

Table 2 presents a comparison of space weather conditions during the three moderate earthquakes, where yellow, red, and orange correspond to the dates of the three earthquakes, which are consistent with Table 1 and Figure 1. The data used to construct Table 2 was obtained from <http://wdc.kugi.kyoto-u.ac.jp/> and <ftp://ftp.swpc.noaa.gov/pub/lists/ace2/>. Solar activity was described using the Wolf numbers W and the index $F_{10.7}$, while the magnetic indices K_p , D_{st} , B_z , and A_p were used to analyse and assess the state of space weather (Pink in the table indicates more intense activity). The results show that the conditions were favourable for observing seismic-ionospheric effects.

Figure 2. Space weather on 1-7 September 2018.

Table 2. State of space weather for July 4 - 10, 2018, September 1 - 7, 2018, April 8 - 14, 2019

July 2018							September 2018							April 2019									
Date	W	F _{10.7}	K _p		D _{st} , nT		A _p	Date	W	F _{10.7}	K _p		D _{st} , nT		A _p	Date	W	F _{10.7}	K _p		D _{st} , nT		A _p
			max	min	max	min					max	min	max	min					max	min			
4	0	68	1+	1-	14	2	4	1	0	68	2	0+	1	-12	4	8	12	79	3+	2-	-5	-27	11
5	0	68	5-	0+	15	-23	17	2	0	68	2	0+	0	-9	4	9	12	79	3+	2-	-1	-21	9
6	0	71	4-	1-	12	-12	7	3	0	68	1+	0+	8	-2	4	10	13	78	4	1	-9	-34	14
7	0	72	2	1-	5	-10	5	4	0	68	3	1-	18	-17	8	11	13	79	3-	1-	-1	-17	6
8	0	72	1+	0+	2	-4	4	5	0	68	3+	1	-4	-23	10	12	14	77	3	1	-1	-21	7
9	0	73	1-	0	4	-2	2	6	0	67	2	0+	11	-13	4	13	14	78	3	0+	0	-17	7
10	0	72	2+	0+	20	0	6	7	0	68	2+	0+	21	-7	4	14	11	75	2-	0+	2	-11	4

It is worth noting that for earthquakes that occurred offshore, larger values of both the geomagnetic index and solar activity index were recorded one day prior to the event. However, for earthquakes that occurred on land, only larger values of the geomagnetic index were recorded, and these values persisted for several days following the earthquake.

4. THE RESULTS OF OBSERVATIONS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Vertical Sounding of the Ionosphere: Ionogram

We used data from the Ionosonde Station in Yamagawa (31.20°N, 130.62°E), which is located at a certain distance from the epicenters of the three earthquakes, for comparative analysis.

Figure 3. Ionograms vertically measured at Yamagawa for UT 18:00 (HH:MM) on 6 July 2018 (a), UT 11:30 on 7 July 2018 (d), UT 18:00 on 4 Sep. 2018 (b), UT 08:30 (g) and UT 18:15 (e) on 5 Sep. 2018, UT 08:30 on 06 (h) and 07 (i) Sep. 2018, UT 18:00 on 10 April 2019 (c) and UT 08:30 on 11 April 2019.

Figures 3d, e and f correspond to the eruption times of the three earthquakes on 7 Jul. 2018, 5 Sep. 2018 and 11 Apr. 2019, respectively. Figures 3a, b and c correspond to the local time JST 03:00:00 before the three earthquakes, respectively. Figures 3g, h and i correspond to the local time JST 17:30:00 on 5, 6, 7 Sep. 2018, respectively. Comparing Figures 3b, e, g, h and i, the structure of ionosphere is affected by the dark terminator. The propagation of gravity waves generated by moderate earthquakes causes changes in the density of electrons in the ionosphere, which can be detected and shown on ionograms Figures 3d, e and f.

4.2 Oblique-Incidence Sounding of the Ionosphere

The behavior of the Doppler spectra on the day of the earthquake and on the control days is noticeably different, shown on Figure 4. At $f_D(t) \approx 0$ Hz, the radio waves were reflected from the stable E or E_s layer.

Take **Hwaseong-Harbin radio path** as an example for illustration. After UT 17:50 on 5 Sep. 2019, significant variations in $f_D(t)$ represents a reflection took place from the F-region of the ionosphere. If the changes in the character of variations at 18:20 and 18:56 are associated with an earthquake, then the observed disturbances correspond to the delay times $\Delta t_1 = 12$ min and $\Delta t_2 = 48$ min. The apparent velocity of propagation of perturbations can be estimated from the following relationship (Guo *etc.*, 2020):

Figure 4. Examples of temporal variations of the Doppler spectra and signal amplitudes at the Hwaseong to Harbin radio path (a,b,c) and for the Goyang to Harbin Radio Propagation Path (d,e,f) on 6, 7 and 9 July 2018 (a,d), on 4 5 and 6 September 2018 (b,e), and on 10, 11 and 12 April 2019 (c, f) (panels from top to bottom). The dashed lines indicate the sunrises (red) and sunsets (blue) at 0- and 100-km altitude.

$$v = \frac{D}{\Delta t_1 - \Delta t_0}, \quad (1)$$

where Δt_0 is the vertical propagation time of the disturbance from the epicenter (Earth's surface) to the ionosphere (i.e., the reflection height up to the E -layer ($z_r \approx 112$ km) and $\Delta t_0 \approx 5.5$ min). The same analysis applies to **Goyang-Harbin radio path**. The values of v and T were used to determine the possible types of waves that could be responsible for transmitting the perturbations. Calculation results are shown in [Table 1](#).

5. CONCLUSIONS

1. Multi-frequency multi-path oblique sounding of the ionosphere was used to analyze the effects of a moderate earthquake in Japan on 5 September 2018. And the observations were checked by ionograms.
2. Differences in the Doppler spectra (DS), Doppler shift, and signal amplitude were observed between the earthquake day on 5 September 2018 and control days. And as a moderate earthquake whose epicenter is on land, its DS is significantly different from that of moderate earthquakes whose epicenters are underwater.
3. Two characteristic apparent perturbation propagation velocities were observed: 3 km/s and about 500 m/s, which are close to the speeds of seismic waves (SWs) and acoustic-gravity waves (AGW) in the Earth's ionosphere, respectively.
4. The effect of the structure of the ionosphere on the propagation of disturbances appears in the form of additional modes/rays on the Doppler spectrum of the HF radio path.
5. Estimates showed that the relative amplitude of N_a in the field of the infrasonic wave and AGW was 1.5–3% ($f_{Da} \approx 0.05$ – 0.10 Hz, $T=3$ min, $\Delta T=30$ min) and 6–7.5% ($f_{Da} \approx 0.20$ – 25 Hz, $T=30$ min, $\Delta T=150$ min), respectively for earthquake on 5 September 2018.
6. These findings suggest that ionospheric and atmospheric disturbances can be used as indicators of seismic activity.
7. Although the studies have further confirmed the relationship between ionospheric perturbations and seismic activity, more efforts are needed to utilize ionospheric data as a reliable and accurate earthquake early warning system.

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References

- Chernogor, L.F. (2011). The Earth–atmosphere–geospace system: main properties and processes. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 32 (11), 3199-3218.
- Chernogor, L.F., Garmash, K.P., Guo, Q., Luo, Y., Rozumenko, V. T. & Zheng, Y. (2020). Ionospheric storm effects over the People's Republic of China on 14 May 2019: Results from multiple path multifrequency oblique radio sounding. *Advances in Space Research*, 66 (2), 226–242.
- Guo, Q., Chernogor, L. F., Garmash, K. P., Rozumenko, V. T. & Zheng, Y. (2019). Dynamical processes in the ionosphere following the moderate earthquake in Japan on 7 July 2018.// *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, 186, 88 – 103.
- Guo, Q., Chernogor, L. F., Garmash, K. P., Rozumenko, V. T. & Zheng, Y. (2020). Radio Monitoring of Dynamic Processes in the Ionosphere over China during the Partial Solar Eclipse of 11 August 2018. *Radio Science*, 55, e2019RS006866.
- Luo, Y., Chernogor, L.F., Garmash, K.P., Guo, Q. & Zheng, Y. (2020a). Seismic-ionospheric effects: results of radio soundings at oblique incidence. *Radio Physics and Radio Astronomy*, 25 (3), 218-230.
- Luo, Y., Chernogor L.F. & Garmash, K.P. (2020b). Geomagnetic effect of Turkish earthquake of January 24, 2020. *Radio Physics and Radio Astronomy*, 25 (4), 276-289.